

A Study on Partially Ordered Sets

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Abstract

In this paper, the notion of derivation on partially ordered sets or posets is introduced and studied. Several examples of posets are presented. The properties of the fixed points based on the derivations are investigated. Finally, the isomorphism of posets and dual posets are studied.

1. Some Results on Posets

1.1. Relations

1.1.1. Definition

Let A, B be two sets. We define $A \times B$ called the *cartesian product* of A and B to the set $A \times B = \{(a, b) | a \in A, b \in B\}$. Any subset of $A \times B$ is called a *relation* from A to B .

For example, if $A = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $B = \{4, 5\}$, then

$$A \times B = \{(1, 4), (1, 5), (2, 4), (2, 5), (3, 4), (3, 5)\}$$
$$R_1 = \{(1, 4), (1, 5)\}, R_2 = \{(2, 4), (2, 5)\}, R_3 = \{(3, 4), (3, 5)\}.$$

1.1.2 Definition

A nonempty set P , together with a binary relation R is said to form a *partially ordered set* or a *poset* if the following conditions hold:

P1: Reflexivity : aRa for all $a \in P$.

P2: Anti-Symmetry: If aRb and bRa then $a = b$ for all $a, b \in P$.

P3: Transitivity : If aRb and bRc then aRc for all $a, b, c \in P$.

Furthermore, if a relation R in P defines a partial order in P , then aRb is denoted by $a \leq b$.

1.1.3 Example

The set N of the natural numbers forms a poset under the usual \leq .

For each $a \in N$, we have $a = a$. It means that $a \leq a$. So \leq is reflexive.

Take any $a, b \in N$, we suppose $a \leq b$ and $b \leq a$.

Then $a = b$. So \leq is anti-symmetric.

Take any $a, b, c \in N$, suppose $a \leq b$ and $b \leq c$.

Then $a \leq c$. Thus \leq is transitive. Hence N forms a poset under usual \leq .

Similarly, we can prove that the set of integers, rationals and real numbers also form a poset under the usual \leq .

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1.1.4 Definition

Let a, b be in a poset. Then we say that a and b are *comparable* if $a \leq b$ or $b \leq a$.

Two elements of a poset may or may not be comparable.

For instance, 2 and 3 are not comparable under divisibility. But 2 and 3 are comparable under usual \leq .

If $a \leq b$ and $a \neq b$, then $a < b$.

1.2 Diagrammatical representation of a poset

To draw the diagram of a poset, we represent

- (1) each element by a small circle (a dot)
- (2) any two comparable elements are joined by lines in such a way that if $a \leq b$, then a lies below b .
- (3) Non-comparable elements are not joined.

Thus, there will not be any horizontal lines in the diagram of a poset.

1.2.1 Example Consider the poset $\{2, 3, 4, 6\}$ under divisibility is represented by Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1

If $X = \{1, 2\}$, then the power set of X ,

$P(X) = \{\emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}\}$ is a poset under \subseteq relation is represented by Figure 1.2

Figure 1.2

(N, \leq) is a poset where \leq is the usual less than or equal to $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ is represented by Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3

1.2.2 Definition

If P is a poset in which every two elements are comparable, then it is called a *totally ordered set* or a *toset* or a *chain*.

Thus if P is a chain and $x, y \in P$, then either $x \leq y$ or $y \leq x$.

1.2.3 Example. A nonempty subset S of a poset P is a poset. If P is a chain, then so is S (under the same \leq , restricted to S).

Indeed if any $a \in S$, then $a \in P$.

Being a poset P , we obtain $a \leq a$. Hence \leq is reflexive.

Take any $a, b \in S$. Then $a, b \in P$. So $a \leq b, b \leq a \Rightarrow a = b$.

Hence \leq is anti - symmetric.

Take any $a, b, c \in S$. Then $a, b, c \in P$.

So $a \leq b, b \leq c \Rightarrow a \leq c$. Hence \leq is transitive.

Therefore (S, \leq) is a poset.

Take any $a, b \in S$. Then $a, b \in P$. Since P is a chain, two elements a and b are comparable.

Hence S is a chain.

1.3 Isomorphism and Related Theorems

1.3.1 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called a *one-to-one correspondence* if it is one-one and onto.

1.3.2 Definition. Let (P, \leq) and (Q, \leq) be two posets. A mapping $f : P \rightarrow Q$ is called *isotone* or *order preserving* if $x \leq y$ implies that $f(x) \leq f(y)$, for all $x, y \in P$.

1.3.3 Definition. Let (P, \leq) and (Q, \leq) be two posets. A one-one onto map $f : P \rightarrow Q$ is called an *isomorphism* if the condition satisfies $x \leq y$ if and only if $f(x) \leq f(y)$, for all $x, y \in P$. In this case, we write $P \cong Q$.

1.3.4 Definition. Let ρ be a relation defined on a set X . The *converse* of ρ (denoted by $\bar{\rho}$) is defined by $a \bar{\rho} b \Leftrightarrow b \rho a$, for all $a, b \in X$.

1.3.5 Theorem (Duality Principal) If a set X forms a poset under a relation ρ then X forms a poset under $\bar{\rho}$, the converse of ρ .

Proof : Let (X, ρ) be a poset. So $a \rho a$ for all $a \in X$.

Thus $a \bar{\rho} a, \forall a \in X$. So $\bar{\rho}$ is reflexive.

Let $a \bar{\rho} b$ and $b \bar{\rho} a$, then $b \rho a$ and $a \rho b$.

i.e, $a \rho b$ and $b \rho a \Rightarrow a = b$. Thus $\bar{\rho}$ is anti-symmetric.

Let $a \bar{\rho} b$ and $b \bar{\rho} c$, then $b \rho a$ and $c \rho b$.

$c \rho b$ and $b \rho a \Rightarrow c \rho a$ (ρ is transitive)

$\Rightarrow a \bar{\rho} c$

Thus $\bar{\rho}$ is transitive. Hence $(X, \bar{\rho})$ is poset.

1.3.6 Definition. If (X, ρ) be a poset, then the poset $(\bar{X}, \bar{\rho})$ is called *dual* of X , where $\bar{X} = X$ and $\bar{\rho}$ is the converse of ρ .

Figure 1.4

The diagram of dual is got by turning the diagram of the original poset upside down.

If (\mathbb{N}, \leq) is a poset, then (\mathbb{N}, \geq) is a dual poset.

1.3.7 Theorem. If (X, ρ) be a poset, then $X \cong \overline{\overline{X}}$ where $\overline{\overline{X}}$ is dual of \overline{X} .

Proof:

Define $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\overline{X}}$ by $f(x) = x, \forall x \in X$

Thus $f(x) = f(y) \Rightarrow x = y$, f is one - one.

Next for every $y \in \overline{\overline{X}}, \exists x \in X$ such that $f(x) = y$.

So f is onto. Again $x \rho y \Leftrightarrow y \bar{\rho} x$

$$\Leftrightarrow x \bar{\bar{\rho}} y$$

$$\Leftrightarrow f(x) \bar{\bar{\rho}} f(y)$$

Thus f is an isomorphism. Hence $X \cong \overline{\overline{X}}$.

Conclusion

We are interested in partial order relations which would finally lead us to the definition of a lattice. We continue our study of the notion of ideals and a distributive lattice.

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